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Integration of Scaffolded Silent Reading on Enhancing Students' Reading Fluency and Comprehension

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Abstract

The average reading scores from PISA 2022 were almost the same as the results from 2018. The Philippines improved by far in reading, but only by seven points, going from 340 to 347 in 2018. However, these results fall short of the OECD average. The percentage of students who scored below a baseline level of competency (Level 2) showed no significant difference from 2018. Hence, the studies' main objective is to employ various approaches that urge the importance of immediately addressing the challenges and gaps in obtaining high-quality basic education in light of the Philippines' low rating. Specifically, this study measured the effectiveness of Scaffolded Silent Reading on eighth-grade students' reading fluency and comprehension. It has adopted the use of Mixed-Methods Sequential Explanatory Design, this strategy is done by delving more thoroughly into the point of view of the participants, analyzing the quantitative and qualitative data to help simplify and improve the results of the statistical analysis. Meanwhile, there were a total of 32 participants, the class was divided into two separate groups: the scaffolded (experimental group) and the non-scaffolded (control group). The study's findings showed that the data on learning gains in fluency and comprehension reveals a significant difference. The experimental group obtained a mean score of 56.13 and the control group was 18.83 on fluency, while on comprehension the experimental group was 25.85 and the control group was 10.31. The experimental group scored higher compared to the other group. The results indicate that Scaffolded Silent Reading is an effective reading strategy as it helps increase the scores of the experimental group after its' utilization. This study thereby recommends its integration into teaching reading.

Keywords: *scaffolded silent reading, fluency, reading comprehension*

Introduction

Reading plays a vital role in every individual's life. It is crucial for establishing an educated society in the world today. In other words, reading is one of the skills needed by an individual to be considered as a literate one. It serves as a primary skill essential in learning and communicating. Unfortunately, many people cannot read well enough to understand and follow the instructions, because not everyone can comprehend.

In the absence of comprehension or without it, reading would be pointless, because the most crucial part of it is comprehending the content. Reading comprehension, according to Brandon (2021), is the capacity to comprehend written language. It is a task to fully comprehend and extrapolate meaning from written content. It implies that understanding is a planned and interactive process. Readers need to engage with the material critically, internalize it, and make it their own. Aside from comprehension, one of the reading skills that students should develop is fluency.

According to Nieporant (2021), fluency serves as a link between recognizing words and comprehending. It is the capacity to read clearly, fluently, and expressively. When students are asked to read aloud, fluent readers sound authentic as if they speak a second language. In contrast, non-fluent readers read over time and sound scratchy which reduces their ability to understand the material. It is important in fluency to read expressively, as a learner one must separate words into smaller parts and use appropriate phrasing since the meaning of the text usually changes when punctuation is ignored. Therefore, fluency and comprehension are important reading skills that students should develop. However, it is difficult for them to master these skills because of unforeseen happenings.

In connection with this, when the pandemic started the learning approach shifted from in-person instruction to virtual sessions. There was a limited time spent on synchronous sessions, teachers were only instructed to give instructions and not to discuss the whole topic. This led to problems that affected the reading skills of students, as they were not given direct assistance and guidance by the teachers. When reading tests were administered, in our school, the scores showed that most of the students failed to get passing grades because of the unfamiliarity with the given words.

Students found it challenging to comprehend the words as it was new to them. But the main problem is whenever a question arises on the text assigned to them, it takes days or a week for it to be addressed. The students were only studying for the sake of passing the grade level. They do not give much importance to improving reading skills, getting average scores is enough. This does not only affect the English subject but also the other academic subjects because the instructions were also written in English.

Moreover, the Philippines received lower scores than the average of participating OECD countries (353 in Mathematics, 357 in Science, and 340 in Reading) in the 2018 PISA results, which were released on December 3, 2019. Filipino pupils performed poorly in the research comparing the reading, science, and math proficiency of 79 participating economies. DepEd acknowledges the necessity of resolving problems and gaps in achieving high-quality basic education in the Philippines as PISA results are based on student's performance on the National Achievement Test (DepEd, 2019).

Compared with the PISA 2022, the average results were about the same as in 2019 in mathematics, reading, and science. Thus, the proportion of students scoring below a baseline level of proficiency (Level 2) showed no significant difference in mathematics, reading, and science. Nearly none of the students in the Philippines achieved reading scores at Level 5 or above (OECD average: 7%). This means that almost no students can comprehend lengthy texts, deal with abstract or counterintuitive concepts, and establish distinctions between fact and opinion, based on implicit cues about the content or source of the information. Thus, poor comprehension is one of the possible reasons for their performance.

Poor comprehension happens when students have difficulty recalling what they have read. It occurs as students experience disinterest and boredom with the reading text provided. Udir (2016) stated that when students encounter challenging words and phrases, in meeting many difficult and unfamiliar words and phrases, the students may become impatient with their reading and feel incompetent. Students tend to decrease their level of productivity towards reading academic texts due to a lack of interest and knowledge. These problems are not only happening in normal classroom setups but are more evident today as shown in the reading performance of the student's last quarter. Thus, one strategy to improve learners' reading abilities, both for comprehension and fluency is through the integration of a reading strategy and this must be present in each crafted lesson plan.

Among the reading strategies, this study intended to use Scaffolded Silent Reading which focuses on the improvement of reading fluency and comprehension. This strategy will give direct instructions and guidance to students in understanding the academic text provided. It supports the importance of allowing students to read interesting texts by providing a variety of materials which increases motivation.

Motivation is a process that initiates someone to continue doing something, without this student becomes passive. At present, the reading program in the school only involves the seventh-grade level, which makes the other grade level behind in terms of reading. This scenario became worse when distance learning was implemented. The researcher personally experienced that students nowadays tend not to engage themselves in reading and are not able to get high scores on reading tests. Analyzing the gathered facts, and integrating Scaffolded Silent Reading is highly recommended as it entails active teacher instruction, coaching, interacting, and student monitoring.

Research Questions

This study's primary purpose is to determine the effectiveness of Scaffolded Silent Reading in enhancing students' reading fluency and comprehension. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What was the performance in the pretest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms:
 - 1.1. fluency;
 - 1.2. comprehension?
2. Was there a significant difference between the performance in the pretest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading on reading fluency and comprehension?
3. What was the performance in the post-test of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms of:
 - 3.1. reading fluency;
 - 3.2. reading comprehension?
4. Was there a significant difference between the performance in the posttest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group?
5. Was there a significant difference in the performance in the pretest and post-test of the non- scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group?
6. Was there a significant difference in the learning gains obtained by the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group?

Literature Review

On Reading

The fundamental component of all educational achievement is reading. The acquisition of reading, writing, and numerical abilities is essential for an individual's academic and personal success. For the past years, experts and researchers have given their definition of reading. It is not just stating the letters in the alphabet but is viewed as one of the fundamental skills that make us understand and convey information. Therefore, it is integrally entwined with the process of learning and instruction.

In the words of Nordquist (2017), reading is the manner of deriving meaning from written or printed material. It starts with word recognition where words are identified, followed by constructing meanings, and then comprehension occurs. He also mentioned that reading stimulates the emergence of novel forms of knowledge and concepts through reader-text interaction.

In addition, Nilamsari (2016) stated that the two fundamental stages of reading are comprehension and decoding. Although these two

procedures are not dependent on one another, literacy requires both of them. Recognizing letter strings and the corresponding units of speech is essential for decoding, which is a way of making sense of printed text. While, comprehension calls for more advanced cognitive and language abilities like intellectual ability, vocabulary, and syntax, which help students make connections with what they read. Thus, to decode and comprehend successfully one must remember that the reading process requires continuous training, development, and improvement.

Moreover, Cando (2018) stated that reading is the essence of acquiring information, while reading comprehension refers to one's capacity to recognize or to read text, to comprehend the meaning, and eventually convert the meaning to the reader's prior knowledge. In this regard, learners and students need to develop and acquire reading skills as it enables them to understand concepts and convey messages.

In support of the previous discussion on reading, Awal (2020) stated that in the twenty-first-century reading is a vital ability. It is not only essential but also a must to be developed as it enables everyone to keep pace with the times. He also mentioned that as the world changes reading is necessary for obtaining information, strengthening skills, and gaining knowledge.

Teaching Reading

Particularly in the industrialized world nowadays, reading is recognized as an indispensable skill necessary for success. Reading is crucial if one wants to have an understanding of what is currently happening in the world at present. Failure to read with comprehension leads to frustrating results.

In the study of Miñoza and Montero (2019), it was stated that developing students who are capable of comprehending and reading the material that is being studied is the primary purpose of educational institutions. They highlighted that one of the main objectives of the educational system is for students to become proficient readers. Nonetheless, it is important to bear in mind that reading is a challenging task, making it tough for teachers to teach and for students to learn.

In the Philippines, the aim of developing fluent readers in students ought not to be seen as a burden that educators must bear alone. Teachers, parents, administrators, and almost every member of society are concerned about it in addition to the students themselves. Still, Cando (2018), stated that one of the responsibilities of educators is to employ a variety of methods, plans, initiatives, and educational materials to enhance student attention, retention, and enjoyment.

Therefore, the implementation of appropriate interventions and programs can have a significant impact on learners. Additionally, a concentrated and organized intervention program can benefit at-risk learners.

Over the years, the research found that enhancing students' reading skills comes from within, which shows that willingness is an important factor to consider. Starke (2020) cited in her article that encouraging children to love reading requires motivation. Books that encompass various genres should be provided to students so they can discover what they enjoy reading the most. Giving students texts that have relevance and connections boosts their perspectives toward reading along with their vocabulary, fluency, and word recognition.

In connection with the above statement, it was mentioned in Krashen's Comprehensible Input Hypothesis that the most effective method in language instruction may be freely voluntary reading. It improves the development of language and literacy and has an immense impact on writing, grammar, vocabulary, and reading comprehension. It is a fun activity that fosters the acquisition of languages.

Krashen further specifies that this kind of reading must be enhanced. It allows readers to have the option of choosing the books that they are genuinely interested in, which makes learning easy. Application of reading strategies with the same objective such as Scaffolded Silent Reading will significantly impact how language skills develop.

Reading Fluency

In the study of Estrada (2016), it has been suggested that oral reading fluency is an accurate measure of reading ability. It has been regarded as a reliable indicator of a student's overall reading proficiency. One critical reading ability that is essential for comprehending material is fluency. Students who struggle with reading are going to find it tough to draw connections and understand the material comprehensively. Developing proficiency in it is significant because it establishes a foundation for reading comprehension.

In addition, Hasbrouck (2016) mentioned that it should be "teaching fluency not speed in reading". Having education that allows students to become highly articulate readers rather than simply speed readers is essential. According to Hasbrouck and Glaser (2012), fluency can be described as "consistently precise reading, at a proper rate, with appropriate expression respectively, that results in correct and profound understanding and willingness for reading." It is having the ability to read explicitly, fluently, and expressively. Word recognition comes naturally to fluent readers; they do not have trouble with decoding (Nieporent, 2021).

Furthermore, one significant indicator of reading comprehension is fluency. Learners can use cognitive methods as they advance in fluency (Rippel, 2019). This suggests that while reading the text, readers can picture, examine, and critically evaluate what they are reading as well as dwell on their own emotions and thoughts. The most advanced reading comprehension level is at this point.

However, fluency grows progressively with practice and time. Students' oral reading is tedious and challenging in the initial phases of their reading growth since they are still discovering how to "break the code," or connect sounds to letters and combine letter sounds to form words that make sense (Partnership for Reading, 2021).

In line with the problems encountered in fluency, Albia and Sonsona (2021), stated that another aspect that has been determined to be affecting the children's reading proficiency is fluency. Findings from their research have resulted in the division of fluency problems into two categories: speedy reading and lengthy reading (an absence of fluency), both of which have a detrimental impact on learners' reading comprehension. Each instructor mentioned that one issue hindering some of their struggling students from completely comprehending a text is a lack of fluency or a delay in decoding. The findings show that when students with learning difficulty read very cautiously and choppy, they are devoting much of their mental capacity and effort to decoding words in a text. They thus begin to misinterpret statements. Not only does reading slowly hamper retention of reading, but reading extremely rapidly also will. Given that they are only concerned with finishing the material they are reading, fast readers overlook the value of the material they are studying.

Fluency is the link between recognizing words and understanding them. If problems in fluency are not addressed, it can negatively influence their reading comprehension. For this reason, effective reading programs that improve fluency skills must be implemented, for readers to readily connect those dots among words, sounds, and meaning.

Reading Comprehension

According to PISA results, just under 25% of Filipino students who took the test in 2022 achieved the minimum level of proficiency in all three subjects—math, reading, and science—despite the education department's flurry of reforms and preparations after a poor performance in PISA 2018. The Philippines may had the biggest improvement in reading but just by seven points, scoring 347 from 340 in 2018. However, according to the OECD, changes in PISA scores of one to two points are not deemed noteworthy, while changes of at least 20 points must correspond to the learning gains or losses of at least a year's worth of education. Thus, poor reading comprehension may be the reason for this low performance.

Reading comprehension, according to RAND Reading Study Group (2002), mentioned by Moore et al. (2016), is the act of concurrently deriving meaning from written language while generating that meaning through participating and interacting with it. It is the course of understanding what you are reading. Likewise, Gaskins (1998) cited by Nilamsari (2016) found that the reader must control the text, task, and situation variables for comprehension to occur. Comprehension means when the student recognizes the material they have been exposed to and realizes that the purpose of reading is to generate meaning,

Furthermore, reading comprehension involves deliberate contemplation in which the reader and the text interact to create meaning. It is when readers intentionally apply critical thinking skills to solve problems, this means that they comprehend the material read (Proepper, 2016). Also, it is a complicated process that demands a proactive connection between the student's previously acquired knowledge, the reading material's goal, and the writers' expertise in the terms and phrases they use for one to fully comprehend a text (Almutairi, 2018).

In support of the previous studies on reading comprehension, Almutairi (2018), also added that for students to achieve success academically and in their personal lives as well, reading comprehension is necessary. The foundation for comprehending all of the material in the educational life of a student is reading comprehension. Additionally, students who are capable of understanding the material that they are reading have the advantage of being likely to find pertinent details quickly, filter all irrelevant information, and decide which major points to concentrate on. In personal life, people who are capable of understanding what they read, proceed through their lives in confidence and thrive both intellectually and socially (Hoeh, 2015).

Reading without comprehension means simply staring at words on a piece of paper and making sounds without understanding them. Additionally, there is no meaning behind what is written on the paper. It comes with mentioning that an individual's educational achievement is negatively affected by poor reading comprehension abilities. The acquisition of information by reading involves learning, evaluation, and practical use of what is being read.

Scaffolded Silent Reading

Scaffolded silent reading is described by Reutzel, Jones, Fawson, and Smith (2008) as the silent, extensive reading of texts chosen at the independent level from a variety of genres; the teacher observation and engagement with particular learners; as well as responsibility through the completion of book response tasks. The course of action covers goal-setting, book selection techniques, being introduced to an extensive spectrum of genres, allocating texts at each student's distinct reading levels, and project completion.

In connection with the previous statement, Fawson et.al (2008) claimed that Sustained Silent Reading, or SSR, reconstructs the conditions whereby silent reading practice happens intending to respond to critiques and issues raised in the past about reading practice while concurrently getting rid with unsuccessful strategies from an earlier time. While ScSR holds certain characteristics with SSR, it also seeks to enhance students' reading comprehension, fluency, and connection with material by constantly tracking their feedback throughout their reading practice.

In an article entitled "Leisure Reading" (2014), studies reveal that reading for leisure demonstrates enhanced comprehension of text,

language proficiency, vocabulary growth, broad expertise, sympathy, as well as positive views on reading. They additionally possess a greater sense of self-worth as readers and have a greater desire to read for the rest of their lives. It only happens when teachers employ reading strategies that support independent reading, one of those is the Scaffolded Silent Reading.

In line with this Cetinkaya (2013) cited by Logston (2015), one way teachers can contribute to the improvement of fluency and comprehension of students during ScSR is by providing them with a list of texts that are in the appropriate difficulty level, by doing this, teachers are creating an environment that students can read the books that they choose. Moreover, not only does the list of appropriate texts improve comprehension and fluency, but it also improves a student's motivation to read, however, teacher support continues to be crucial for students to be successful in reading (Melekoğlu, 2013).

In addition, based on the study of Nilamsari (2016), some students who do not like English cannot maximally do the activities in the class. However, after employing the ScSR approach some students like to read more and the existence of the school library looks very useful to them. It also stated that Scaffolded Silent Reading is an efficient approach for enhancing students' comprehension of texts.

Similarly, Proepper (2016) stated that certain learners expressed their satisfaction with the peaceful, focused reading time frame, emphasizing that it enabled them to concentrate on the material they were reading without getting interrupted by other events that were going place throughout the classroom.

However, the application of ScSR is not always successful, in contrast with the positive feedback on ScSR, a study by Logston (2015), showed that students' scores who participated in 20 minutes of scaffolded silent reading three times a week did not vary significantly with those who did not. On the other hand, there were only eleven students involved in the study, and the data was only collected for a month. Thus, it shows that if this study is to be conducted on a larger scale for a longer period, the results will be different.

Synthesis

Various literature and studies were reviewed and analyzed to present an in-depth overview of the research. Reading is indeed a fundamental skill that each learner needs to develop. This is required to be mastered as it is essential to understand concepts and convey messages. Literature and studies included in the study showed that comprehension and fluency are very important aspects when it comes to reading, and they go hand in hand when determining a child's success in reading.

Previous studies revealed that fluency and comprehension are interconnected. Fluency is an essential skill to have since it establishes the foundation for understanding what you are reading. Proficient or fluent readers have more time to comprehend a text, while non-fluent readers find it difficult to get the message as they focus on decoding. If problems in fluency are not addressed, it can negatively influence their reading comprehension. Therefore, findings indicated the use of different approaches in promoting reading is necessary.

As indicated in the mentioned studies, the most effective way of teaching reading comes from willingness. This means that students who view reading as an enjoyable activity are much more likely to experience success as readers. It was stated that students tend to decrease their level of productivity towards reading academic text due to a lack of interest and knowledge, which means that choosing an academic text is effective when students' choices are considered. All the mentioned studies show that motivation is an important factor for students to continue reading, and this can be achieved if their interest is considered.

The previous studies and literature showed that one of the reading strategies, that considers the interest of learners which leads to motivation is the use of Scaffolded Silent Reading. Most of the studies that integrated ScSR agreed on its effectiveness. It shows that it helps students develop reading comprehension as well as fluency. Through this strategy, reading becomes an enjoyable activity which leads to better results. However, one study disagrees, as it revealed that using ScSR does not improve the reading skills of the student. But it was also mentioned that in integrating ScSR, this must be taken over a longer period and must be strictly monitored. It requires a lot of patience to be implemented, and effectiveness can only be seen if effort is visible.

Normally, Scaffolded Silent Reading is used in a normal classroom setup, where teachers and students interact physically. Now, the challenge is to integrate this strategy into online distance learning, wherein some programs are not implemented because of the difficulty. In our school, there is no existing reading intervention, especially at the higher grade level. When students fail to get a passing grade in reading activities, it cannot be addressed directly. Therefore, this study must be conducted to determine whether or not Scaffolded Silent Reading is beneficial. Eventually, it may be used as one of the interventions for struggling readers. It only takes a well-crafted plan, with clear procedures, validated instruments, and the commitment of a teacher to apply the strategy.

Methodology

Research Design

This study has adopted the use of Mixed-Methods Sequential Explanatory Design by Creswell. Tegan (2022) stated that this strategy entails gathering quantitative data initially, followed by qualitative data to support or expand on the statistical findings. Thus, by delving more thoroughly into the point of view of the participants, the quantitative and qualitative data, added to the analysis, help simplify and improve the results of the statistical analysis.

In collecting the quantitative data, the researcher used one of the types of Quantitative Research which is the Experimental method.

Among the subtypes of Experimental Designs, the true experimental method was utilized. The most formidable and most reliable type of experimental research is considered to be true experimental design. As an outcome of the true experiment's extensive influence over known confounding factors, the results about the relationship between causes and effects can be considered more credible (Ghai, Rana & Sharma, 2019). A True experimental design is named so under three important properties: Manipulation, Control, and Random Assignment. While there are numerous ways to utilize true experimental designs, the Pretest-Posttest Control group Design will be applied in this study. By testing a link between cause and effect, this method works great. Two groups of equal size have been included in the design because they were selected randomly. The experimental group represents the only one that undergoes treatment, whereas the control group is the group that does not get any treatment. On the other hand, as a way to gain an improved understanding of the numerical results, the researcher applied the open-ended interview as one of the methods under Qualitative Research. This helps strengthen and further support the data gathered.

Participants

The researcher applied a systematic sampling technique in selecting the study participants, to achieve the purpose of no bias in assigning the participants, among the methods of sampling randomly. In employing this strategy, samples are selected from a wider group. Fixed intervals among each participant are applied in the procedure for sampling, considering the initial starting point might seem random. To calculate the sampling interval here use the formula $i=N/n$. Where N represents the population scale, while n is the sample scale (David, 2017).

The research was carried out at Paliparan II Integrated High School in the City of Dasmariñas, Cavite. The subjects came from the eighth-grade level. It has a total number of 32 participants.

From a total of 32 participants, and by using the formula of systematic sampling method in dividing the class into two groups, 2 is the sampling interval. Using the sampling interval, the 16 students of the class were designated as the control group and the remaining 16 were the experimental group. To make sure that there is a valid point in conducting the study, the preceding criteria were applied in determining the participants. First, these students are currently enrolled in the low-performing class at Paliparan II Integrated High School. Second, they are grade 8 students handled by the researcher. Lastly, in their English subject, most of the learners showed a satisfactory level from the previous quarter.

Instrument

To gather valuable data and information the researcher used the following instruments and techniques:

Questionnaires. The researcher adopted questionnaires from easyCBM that focus on testing fluency and comprehension. With the assistance of highly qualified instructors from three distinct departments and institutions. The questionnaire used was examined to make sure that it will help in measuring students' skills in reading comprehension and fluency. It was also made sure that these questionnaires will test the reading skills connected to the MELCs mandated by DepEd.

Pre-test and Post-test. Students' reading comprehension was evaluated before and after the interventions using the easyCBM Multiple Choice Reading Comprehension. The purpose of the easyCBM examinations is to measure students' evaluative, inferential, and literal comprehension.

The easy CBM Passage Reading Fluency was employed for evaluating the reading fluency of the individuals being studied before as well as after the interventions. Accuracy and fluency within material appropriate for the grade are taken into consideration in the above assessment. The test will be provided to each student independently, then they will be reading a passage aloud for one minute (Proepper, 2016).

Open-ended Interview. Apart from the Online Survey Questionnaire, the open-ended interview was also used to strengthen and further support the data gathered using the survey instrument. It was used in the study as a means of follow-up. The questions asked in a standardized open-ended interview are written in an extremely organized manner. In the present study, participants are asked precisely the same questions, but the structure of the questions promotes broad responses (Gall, Gall, & Borg, 2003). Furthermore, it helped the researcher reveal the problems encountered by the respondents during the assessment as well as the personal effects of the program on them.

Individual Monitoring Conference Form. To monitor individual reading from the start until the last part of the study, this Individual Monitoring Conference Form was employed. The purpose of this is to record and track meetings with the students. The researcher recorded students' oral reading on the IMC form, monitoring the reading rate while making certain that the material was at an independent level. Instructions for the comprehension session and goal-setting with students were also provided by the IMC.

Construction. The researcher adopted questionnaires but before using them, it was validated first by the experts in English. It was made sure that the adopted questionnaire from the easyCBM was aligned with the learning competencies for the fourth quarter in terms of reading.

Validation. After all the instruments prepared by the researcher were needed for the study, she sought assistance from her other subject experts to validate the questionnaire, lesson plans, and rubric if it is relevant to the said study. Their comments and suggestions were

considered in adopting the questionnaire, in crafting lesson plans, and in constructing the rubric used for fluency.

Reliability. After the instrument's validation, a Pilot test was executed by the researcher to increase the questionnaire's quality and its potential to achieve the objective of the research process (Gudmundsdottir & Brock-Utne, 2010). After the researcher organized the data gathered, it was subjected to the Cronbach alpha test. In 2010, Sekaran and Bougie stated that the most widely used test of inter-item consistency reliability is Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Therefore, the internal consistency of the instrument was measured using Cronbach's alpha test. Once the data was processed through SPSS, it was determined that the tool was reliable with a Cronbach alpha of 0.7.

Procedure

First, to ensure that the conduct of the research will follow maximum protocols for the safety of the respondents who will be involved in the study, an Ethics review was sought from the Office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs Research and Publication of the National Teachers College. Secondly, the researcher obtained approval for administering the tests for comprehension and fluency assessments by submitting a letter to the Office of the Division Superintendent about the study.

After obtaining the permit to execute the study, the consent letter to the parents was given and all the necessary materials were prepared. Next, the researcher conducted a meeting with the research participants. Subsequently, the class was separated into two groups: the controlled group and the experimental group.

The researcher prepared the materials needed for the study such as the following: google applications, individual monitoring conference form, lesson plans, rubric, and the easyCBM assessments for reading fluency and comprehension. The study started from the first and last week of the fourth quarter, with a total of seven weeks.

In the first week, the measuring instruments (pre-test) were administered to the participants. Within the span of a week, every student underwent an individual fluency assessment for which they were required to read a single passage for a duration of one minute, all online meetings were recorded with students' and parents' consent.

The entire class completed the comprehension assessment. After reading the narrative, participants were given time to think through what they answered. Upon completion, the researcher gathered and graded every assessment. This was done through meetings and Google Forms.

After the preliminary assessments, to start the study's initial phase, students in the experimental group were engaged in the integration of Scaffolded Silent Reading. In a scheduled time daily, students pick their reading text from the selections in the lessons of the fourth quarter, with the guidance of the teacher, then read independently for ten to twenty minutes. All reading texts posted were guided by the DepEd curriculum, considering the competencies needed to be attained for the quarter. The strategy was reflected in each lesson plan for seven weeks. While students were reading the teacher conducted the use of Individual Monitoring Conference Form every day, involving from four to five learners. The students were monitored each time every week for fluency, comprehension, and reading text completion in the coming seven weeks. The average number of hours required for Junior High School students was 4 hours a day. This was considered in the conduct of the study. Each of the participants only spent at least two hours a day, it already includes some of the subjects attended on that day. Also, the intervention was done every afternoon since synchronous sessions for academic subjects are spent in the morning. And last week the researcher administered the easyCBM measures (post-test), just like how the pretest was conducted. The researcher personally gathered all the data using Google applications.

Meanwhile, students who were under the controlled group were subjected to the usual flow of the lesson each week without the integration of the ScSR.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher addressed the study's possible risks by obtaining the Research Ethics Committee's clearance through all required stages and procedures prior to data collection. Guidelines for informing participants about the study's purpose and results, a plan for informing them of their inclusion in the study, assurances regarding the privacy and security of sensitive data, a consent form for their voluntary participation in the study, a discussion of ethical issues in the event that the study involves sensitive topics, a detailed plan to maintain the confidentiality and anonymity of participants and potentially affected individuals, compliance with the Data Protection Law, and ethical considerations were all part of the process.

Results and Discussion

What was the performance in the pretest of the non- scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms of: Fluency

According to Hasbrouck and Glaser (2012), fluency has been defined as justifiably correct reading, at a proper rate, with suitable expression respectively, which results in precise and profound understanding and willingness to read. Also, Nieporent (2021) stated that this refers to the capacity for clear, smooth, and expressive reading. In this study, competencies measured under fluency are the following: phrasing, pacing, smoothness, and volume and expression. In measuring, expression and volume, one must know that this

is the ability to match the tone and mood of the reading material to sound varied and conversational. Then, phrasing is the ability to chunk words into phrases. On the other hand, smoothness is the ability to read material smoothly and pause only when appropriate. While pacing refers to the rate at which the student reads.

Table 1. *Performance in the Pretest of the Non- Scaffolded Silent Reading Group and the Scaffolded Silent Reading Group in terms of Fluency*

Group	Standard deviation	Mean	Verbal Description
Scaffolded	3.65	11.56	Developing Reader
Non-scaffolded	1.78	12.63	Developing Reader

As reflected in Table 1 the performance in the pretest of the non-scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms of fluency. As gleaned from the table, the mean score of the non- scaffolded group is 12.63 with a standard deviation of 1.78. While the scaffolded group has a mean score of 11.56 with a standard deviation of 3.65. These two groups have mean scores that were described as developing readers. In support, Morrison and Wilcox (2020) also used the four components present in assessing reading fluency. The findings indicate that the overall mean score was 12.54 out of 16, with the mean scores on expression and volume being 3.11, phrasing being 3.25, smoothness being 3.12, and tempo being 3.06. In comparison with the recent study, the mean for both groups 11.56 and 12.63 was relatively close. The results of each component's scores can be examined thus providing teachers with detailed information regarding their students' strengths and difficulties, which may help them determine choices about the most effective ways to educate their students.

Hasbrouck (2016) mentioned it is critical to provide learning that ensures students develop into highly fluent readers instead of only becoming speed readers. It should be teaching fluency not speed in reading. Fluency could not be shown by students reading rapidly without giving careful attention to expression, punctuation, or comprehension. Although raising students' reading rates is crucial, comprehension should not be compromised throughout the process.

Moreover, the result implies that most of the students are not considered struggling readers but developing readers, which means that there is an area for improvement at the very beginning. Here reading fluency was not only measured based on speed but this includes one's phrasing, stress, pitch, and rhythm.

Comprehension

Table 2. *Performance in the pretest of the Non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms of Comprehension*

Group	Standard Deviation	Mean	Verbal Description
Scaffolded	3.181	11.38	Good
Non-scaffolded	4.266	11.06	Good

Moore, et al. (2016) described comprehension as simply the method of connecting with written material as an attempt to effectively extract and construct meaning. Comprehension starts when the student recognizes the text they have read and discovers that the purpose of reading is to generate meaning. In assessing comprehension, multiple-choice reading comprehension was used in the study. From the twenty given questions, the following competencies were measured: getting the main idea, drawing conclusions, comparing, making inferences, noting details, and forming generalizations. Using the Table of Specification, these competencies were classified based on their cognitive dimension, namely: evaluation, synthesis, analysis, application, comprehension, and knowledge.

Table 2 displays the performance in the pretest of the non-scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms of comprehension. The mean score of the scaffolded group is 11.38 with a standard deviation of 3.181. While the non-scaffolded group has a mean score of 11.06 with a standard deviation of 4.266. The scores of the two groups were interpreted as good which means they can determine the text's central idea and some additional information. However, they find it challenging to come up with judgments and give convincing evidence. Furthermore, they can only interpret words in familiar settings.

In addition, the result shows that among the cognitive dimension comprehension and analysis have the lowest number of correct answers. While the highest score goes to questions under knowledge. This implies that it is difficult for the students to answer when it requires Higher-Order Thinking Skills. This result is somehow alarming because as Almutairi (2018), stated for students to thrive and to achieve success both academically and personally, reading comprehension is a necessity. If reading comprehension is present, students can identify relevant information quickly, eliminate unnecessary content from what is currently being discussed, and figure out which information is essential for them to concentrate on. Apart from that, an individual's academic achievement will be influenced by poor reading comprehension skills. Since comprehension, analysis, and application of the knowledge obtained through reading are essential for educational advancement

Was there a significant difference between the performance in the pretest of the non- scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading on reading fluency and comprehension?

As presented in Table 3 the t-value for the pretest results from independent samples on fluency between non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups shows that there is no significant difference in the pretest scores of these groups as revealed by the t-value of 1.046 with a p =

0.304 > 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3. *Test of Difference between the Pretest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading Group and the Scaffolded Silent Reading on Reading Fluency*

Group	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Non-scaffolded	12.63	1.78	1.046	0.304	Not Significant	Accept
Scaffolded	11.56	3.65				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

In the research findings of Saaris (2016), it was shown that there is a significant difference between the pre-test of the controlled and experimental groups. Comparatively speaking, in the current study the difference between the mean scores was 1.07 wherein the non-scaffolded scored higher than the scaffolded group. The pre-test results provided the researcher with helpful details regarding the students' comprehension and knowledge of the reading material. As the program has only begun, this provides the opportunity to assess the student's prior learning, prepare them for upcoming classes, and eventually monitor their progress after the intervention's completion.

Table 4. *Test of Difference between the Pretest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading Group and the Scaffolded Silent Reading on Reading Comprehension*

Group	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Non-scaffolded	11.06	4.27	-0.235	0.816	Not Significant	Accept
Scaffolded	11.38	3.18				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

As displayed in Table 4 the t-value for the pretest results from independent samples on comprehension between non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups. As shown in the table, there is no significant difference in the pretest scores of these groups as revealed by the t-value of -0.235 with a $p = 0.816 > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

In the the study results of Kurt (2020), it was also stated that under reading comprehension there is a significant difference between the pre-test of the controlled and experimental groups. However, findings of the current study indicate that there is no significant difference that occurs between the two groups' mean scores.

The findings gave the idea of student's reading comprehension capacities and limitations, as well as the knowledge that the students already have. It challenges the researcher to focus on what students need to learn and where changes need to be made to improve students' ability to comprehend.

What was the performance in the post-test of the non- scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms of:

Reading Fluency

Table 5. *Performance in the Posttest of the Non- Scaffolded Silent Reading Group and the Scaffolded Silent Reading Group in terms of Reading Fluency*

Group	Standard Deviation	Mean	Verbal Description
Scaffolded	2.553	13.62	Fluent Readers
Non-scaffolded	1.461	13.00	Developing Readers

Estrada (2016) mentioned that reading proficiency is likely to be accurately predicted by oral fluency in reading. It was acknowledged as a valid measure of student's general reading skills. And an essential ability to possess as it builds the foundation for reading comprehension. In connection to this, Albia and Sonsona (2021) claimed that a number of their students experiencing challenges with learning struggle to comprehend a text correctly due to a poor level of fluency.

The findings reveal that children tend to lose the actual meaning of sentences once they read choppy and slowly. Students who are fast readers overlook the important aspects of the material they are reading because they are only concerned with completing the material they are currently reading. Therefore, in improving one's reading fluency, practice is a must because when not taught properly, this will negatively impact the understanding of reading.

As reflected in Table 5 the performance in the posttest of the non-scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group in terms of fluency. As gleaned from the table, the mean score of the non- scaffolded group is 13.00 with a standard deviation of 1.461 and described as developing readers. While the scaffolded group has a mean score of 13.62 with a standard deviation of 2.553 and is described as fluent readers. In comparison with the group's previous mean scores with the results of the pre-test and the post-test. The scaffolded group scored higher than the non-scaffolded group. After the post-test, developing readers were described as fluent readers. While the control group was still described as developing readers.

The result was supported by the study of Nilamsari (2016), after the integration of Scaffolded Silent Reading the number of scores improved on fluency among the scaffolded group in comparison with the non- scaffolded group. It was also mentioned that some

students who do not like reading now become someone who likes to read more, and the existence of the school library looks very useful to them.

Based on the findings scaffolding can be a tool or an aid for growth to achieve learner's independence in reading. The scores may not show a big difference, but the improvements in students' performance in reading fluency suggest the positive effect of the reading strategy. Thus, scaffolding can be a helpful tool when teaching children to read with greater accuracy reading comprehension

Cando (2018) stated that reading comprehension refers to one's capacity to recognize or to read text, comprehend the meaning, and eventually convert the meaning to the reader's prior knowledge. This is a complicated procedure that necessitates a constant connection between the reading material's target, the student's prior background understanding, and the writers' proficiency in both the language and vocabulary used to understand a book (Almutairi, 2018).

Table 6. Performance in the Posttest of the Non- Scaffolded Silent Reading Group and the Scaffolded Silent Reading Group in terms of Reading Comprehension

Group	Standard deviation	Mean	Verbal Description
Scaffolded	2.798	13.69	Very Good
Non-scaffolded	3.098	12.50	Good

As displayed in Table 6 the comprehension performance of the scaffolded silent reading group and the non-scaffolded silent reading group in the post-test. As gleaned from the table, the scaffolded group's mean score is 13.69 with a standard deviation of 2.798 and is described as very good. This means that students can determine the material's basic idea and details to it. Provide written evidence that supports judgments. However, generating assumptions is limited, and students are experiencing difficulty in understanding unfamiliar phrases.

In comparison with the previous score, the result of the post-test is higher which means there was an improvement. In connection with the result, an article entitled Leisure Reading (2014) confirmed that studies reveal that students who read for enjoyment have enhanced reading comprehension, language proficiency, vocabulary growth, broad understanding, compassion, and positive views on reading. They additionally possess higher self-esteem as readers and have a greater drive to continue reading for their entire lives. It only happens when teachers employ reading strategies that support independent reading, one of those is the Scaffolded Silent Reading.

On the other hand, the non-scaffolded group has a mean score of 12.50 with a standard deviation of 3.098 and is described as still good. The mean scores increased compared with the previous result in the pre-test. However, it was not that high which still resulted in the same interpretation with pre-test scores. This implies that the performance of the non-scaffolded group showed no improvement.

As the result shows scaffolding when applied in reading helps learners develop a higher level of comprehension. It serves as an aid for students to achieve independence in reading. And, to attain learners' success in reading, they must comprehend the material they read while finding pleasure in participating in the reading activity, learn from it, and realize what they have learned, this only happens when strategies like this are applied when teaching reading may it be fluency or comprehension.

Was there a significant difference between the performance in the posttest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group?

Table 7. Test of Difference between the Posttest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading Group and the Scaffolded Silent Reading on Reading Fluency

Group	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Non-scaffolded	13.00	1.461	-.850	.402	Not Significant	Accept
Scaffolded	13.63	2.553				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

As displayed in Table 7 the t-value for the posttest results from independent samples on fluency between non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups. The table indicates that there is no significant difference in the pretest scores of these groups as revealed by the t-value of -.850 with a $p = 0.402 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The study respondents' statements verified this as well during the interview. Statements are as follows:

P1: "At this time, I'm fine, because I was under pressure earlier while taking the exam. I was having a panic attack again."

P3: "I'm not doing fine; we are under quarantine because my father tested positive from COVID-19. Everyone at home was not feeling well. I just also felt the symptoms a while ago."

These imply that participants of the study felt pressured while taking the test because they had some situations that affected their focus such as having family-related issues and mental health concerns. Therefore, the performance of the participants was affected by the external factors. As Nordquist (2017) conducted his study results of the scores were also negatively affected because of the problems encountered by the students when taking their assessment. Some were emotionally distressed which led to the loss of focus, which also happened in the current study.

Table 8. *Test of Difference between the Posttest of the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading Group and the Scaffolded Silent Reading on Reading Comprehension*

Group	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Non-scaffolded	12.50	3.098	-1.138	.264	Not Significant	Accept
Scaffolded	13.69	2.798				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

Table 8 displays the results of the t-test for independent samples of the post-test on comprehension between the non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups. As gathered from the table, there is no significant difference in the pretest scores of these groups as revealed by the t-value of -1.138 with a $p = 0.264 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

In connection to this, the result was also corroborated by the study participants' statements during the interview. Statements are as follows:

P2: "I'm not feeling well mam, but I finished the exam even though I blanked out several times, I don't want my scores to drop. I was under medication because two weeks ago I was diagnosed with depression. Last Monday I scheduled an appointment with my doctor."

P4: "I'm sad while taking the exam because I was thinking that it's my last year at Paliparan as a student because we're moving to New Zealand."

P5: "Now it's better mam, but earlier I wasn't because while I was answering I couldn't focus. I was watching my brother."

These indicate that the performance of the participants was affected because they were unable to concentrate due to depression, which resulted in the loss of focus. The feeling of loneliness and anxiousness was also mentioned which leads to emotional distress aside from the mental health concerns. If someone is experiencing the same negative situations this will affect one's performance.

As Cherry (2022) stated anxiety and psychological stress might influence exam achievement. Overwhelming nervousness could interfere with concentration and make it hard to remember what has been studied. Someone might encounter an intellectual obstacle that prohibits them from comprehending all of the material that have invested an extensive time analyzing. Even if someone knows the answer a person may blank out the answers to those questions.

Was there a significant difference in the performance in the pretest and post-test of the non- scaffolded silent reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group?

Table 9. *Test of Difference between the Pretest and Post-test of the Scaffolded Silent Reading Group*

Test type	Mean	Std deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Pretest	11.56	3.651	-5.257	0.000	Significant	Reject
Posttest	13.00	2.553				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

As reflected in Table 9 the t-test for paired samples findings of the pretest and post-test on fluency for the scaffolded group. As gleaned from the table, the pretest and posttest scores of the scaffolded group showed significant differences as revealed by the t-value of -5.257 with a $p = 0.000 > 0.05$. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The outcome of the findings was supported by Nilamsari (2016), claiming that the study's mean for the experimental group was 76.19, whereas the comparison group's mean was 62.61. The post-test mean for the experimental group was greater compared to the mean of the comparison group. Further, it indicates that the comparison group's achievement was lower when compared to the experimental group. Based on the post- test results along with the application of the strategy, it can be concluded that scaffolded silent reading is an effective strategy for enhancing students' reading comprehension.

However, Logston (2015) conducted his study regarding Scaffolded Silent Reading that shows no significant difference in the student's test scores who were subjected to the experimental group and those who were not.

Most of the studies that integrated Scaffolded Silent Reading agreed on its effectiveness. It only shows that this helps students develop reading comprehension as well as fluency. Through this strategy, reading becomes an enjoyable activity which leads to better results. However, when there is no monitoring as well as not taken for a longer period, the result may lead to a significant difference.

Table 10. *Test of Difference between the Pretest and Post-test of the Non-scaffolded Silent Reading Group*

Test type	Mean	Std deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Pretest	12.63	1.784	-0.752	0.464	Not Significant	Accept
Posttest	13.00	1.461				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

As shown in Table 10 the t-test for paired samples findings of the fluency pretest and posttest for the non- scaffolded group indicates no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the non-scaffolded group as revealed by the t-value of -0.752 with a $p = 0.464 > 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

The findings imply, that students will demonstrate improvement and growth in reading even after a series of lessons, but without the employment of any teaching strategy, the results of the scores will not be significantly different. In connection with this, when PISA 2018 results were released, wherein it was reviewed that in the reading, science, and math competency of 79 participating countries, Filipino learners performed poorly. Thus, DepEd acknowledges the necessity of taking action to solve gaps and issues to ensure that fundamental learning in the Philippines attains the highest possible quality. A method to enhance students' reading skills, both for comprehension and fluency is through the integration of a reading strategy and this must be present in each crafted lesson plan.

Cando (2018) stated that a teacher must employ numerous approaches, plans, projects, and instructional materials that boost the value, effectiveness, and enjoyment of learning. Therefore, the implementation of appropriate interventions and programs can have a significant impact on learners. On top of that, an in-depth and well-planned intervention program may aid at-risk learners.

Was there a significant difference in the learning gains obtained by the non- Scaffolded Silent Reading group and the scaffolded silent reading group?

Table 11. *Learning Gains on Fluency*

Group	Mean	Std deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Non- scaffolded	18.83	6.90	-3.438	0.002	Significant	Reject
Scaffolded	56.13	8.37				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

As presented in Table 11 the learning gains result in fluency between non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups. The table reveals that the learning gains of these groups indicates that there is a significant difference as revealed by the t-value of -3.438 with a $p = 0.002 > 0.05$. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

It implies the idea in which the scaffolded group, in comparison with the non-scaffolded group improved its performance on reading fluency based on the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores. This only means that integrating scaffolded silent reading helps students in gaining and acquiring new skills in fluency. The impressive results emerged through an overall increase in the assessment scores on phrasing, smoothness, pace, expression and volume, and smoothness. As stated by Miñoza and Montero (2019), Scaffolded Silent Reading helps learners be proficient in reading, it was an exceedingly challenging approach, thus making it a difficult skill to teach, but students' scores showed significant differences in terms of learning gains after the utilization.

This was also supported by the students during the interview. Statements are as follows:

P1: "For the past two months po mam, I was able to gain confidence, most especially to read aloud"

P2: "I don't stutter anymore while reading"

This only signifies that when students are monitored and given activities that enable them to be in charge of their own learning just like letting them read aloud and provide feedback, independent reading can be achieved which leads to fluency.

Table 12. *Learning Gains on Comprehension*

Group	Mean	Std deviation	t-value	Sig. value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Non- scaffolded	10.31	18.02	-2.318	0.027	Significant	Reject
Scaffolded	25.85	19.85				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

Table 12 presents the learning gains results on comprehension between non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups. The table indicates a significant difference in the learning gains of these groups as revealed by the t-value of -2.318 with a $p = 0.027 > 0.05$. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Assessing the findings of pre-test and post-test scores, the scaffolded group improved its performance on reading comprehension as revealed in the learning gains. The growth in the students' performance is shown when their scores increase in comparison with the previous score on comprehension. It also shows that students develop higher-order thinking skills as the cognitive dimension with the highest score is evaluation. While the non- scaffolded group showed no significant difference in its learning gains. This implies that students who were intervened using the Scaffolded Silent Reading gained improvement in comprehension than those who were not subjected to any intervention.

In support of the study of Proepper (2016), results reveal that the learning gains of the controlled and experimental groups showed a significant difference. Wherein the experimental group surpassed the final score of the non-experimental group, especially in comprehension.

In addition, this was also reflected in the students' responses during the interview. Statements are as follows:

P3: "I'm able to gain new words and use the unfamiliar words in a sentence"

P4: "I was challenged to read more books and stories because I found a new hobby in reading" P5: "It was positive, I enjoyed the

session because it helped me improve my comprehension, I also recommend this program to those who are struggling in reading, this will help them practice developing their skills”

The integration of Scaffolded Silent Reading as a strategy contributes to the improvement of students' reading comprehension skills. This provides a positive impact that led to its recommendation to be used as an aid for struggling readers.

Conclusions

This part concludes the findings on the Integration of Scaffolded Silent Reading on Enhancing Students' Reading Fluency and Comprehension. In line with the foregoing findings, a conclusion had been drawn and encapsulated by the researcher.

The overall performance of both groups during the pre-test was described as developing reader in terms of fluency which means students demonstrated the ability to read aloud with expression. However, the reader sees certain terms and/or phrase constructions challenging for them to comprehend. On the other hand, students were described with good comprehension which means that they can determine the material's basic idea, as well as a few details about it, but still struggle in providing evidence that supports judgments as well as giving assumptions. They can only, identify words they are familiar with.

The student's performance between the pretest scores of non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups in fluency as well as in comprehension showed no significant difference.

The overall performance of the scaffolded group during the post-test is described as fluent reader in terms of fluency which means students can read with a range of expression and loudness. Thereby, they can read fluently with minimal pauses, but self-corrects whenever faced with challenging words or phrase structures. Also, they can read the entire text at a conversational rate. While, in comprehension, they were described as very good which means they can determine the material's basic idea and details to it, as well as provide written evidence that supports judgments. On the other hand, the non-scaffolded group is described as developing readers and having good comprehension and, the same interpretation with its pre- test scores.

The student's performance for both scores in the post-test of non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups in fluency as well as in comprehension during the post-test revealed no significant difference.

The scaffolded group's performance in the pretest and posttest results displayed significant differences. This supported the claims that the integration of Scaffolded Silent Reading contributes to enhancing students' skills in fluency and comprehension. On the other hand, the non-scaffolded group's pretest and posttest scores revealed no significant difference.

The learning gains in fluency and comprehension between the non-scaffolded and scaffolded groups showed significant differences. Compared to the non-scaffolded group, the scaffolded group's mean scores were noticeably greater upon the integration of Scaffolded Silent Reading. This was supported by the learning gains and the students' increment in the pretest to the post-test performance. Hence, this proved that Scaffolded Silent Reading is an effective and efficient strategy for enhancing the reading fluency and comprehension skills of the students.

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